

Can Youth-Centric News Portals Influence Governance Through Citizen Journalism?

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ABSTRACT

I have always been passionate about journalism, which made me excited to explore this project. In today's world, we consume news every day, and I've noticed many young people from Gen Z creating their own news pages to share updates, raise awareness, and highlight social issues. This made me wonder: can these youth-centric news portals actually influence governance through citizen journalism? To investigate, I conducted a survey with 50 respondents aged 15–30 and analyzed reports on digital activism. The results show that while youth engagement clearly raises awareness and encourages discussions, it rarely leads to direct changes in government policies. This study also suggests ways to strengthen the impact of youth-led digital media, so their voices can have a stronger influence on decision-making.

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital era, news reaches us almost instantly, and young people are increasingly shaping what gets shared and discussed online.

But in order to figure out what's reliable and what's not we need to understand a lot of key terms and differences that are very vital to judge specific news with responsibility and awareness.

Youth-centric news portals are very common these days and you will often find them around you but what does it really mean? If I had to break down into simple words it's basically online platforms designed for young audiences or run by young people themselves.

These portals are widely shaped by citizen journalism which refers to ordinary individuals sharing news or highlighting issues online.

Now comes the most important aspect that is governance which means a way in which governments make decisions and deliver public services.

With Gen Z increasingly taking initiatives by opening news pages and campaigns online, it becomes important to understand whether these efforts can influence governance and policy-making which is what exactly this study focuses on.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

To understand youth-centric news portals and their popularity among young audiences.

To analyze the role of citizen journalism in shaping public opinion and influencing governance.

To evaluate the impact of youth participation in news sharing on decision-making and accountability.

RESEARCH QUESTION AND HYPOTHESIS

Research Question

How does youth participation in citizen journalism through youth-centric news portals influence public opinion and governance?

Hypothesis

Youth engagement in citizen journalism via youth-centric news portals positively impacts public awareness and contributes to more accountable governance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to **Oh Yeon-ho (2000)**, citizen journalism means that “every citizen is a reporter,” where ordinary people share news using digital platforms. It grew rapidly with the rise of the internet and social media, allowing instant reporting from across the world. Platforms like **OhmyNews** showed how citizens can actively participate in news creation. Citizen journalism has also played an important role in political events by spreading information and bypassing censorship. However, it raises concerns about the reliability and accuracy of information.

According to **Bharadwaj (2017)**, **citizen journalism** allows ordinary people to report news through the internet and social media, making information instantly accessible worldwide. It strengthens democracy by giving every individual a voice and broadening coverage, especially in conflict zones. However, it raises concerns about **credibility, bias, and legal issues**, as citizen journalists lack professional training. Despite its pros and cons, citizen journalism has become an important source of information, highlighting the need for responsible reporting.

Authors like **Mishra and Krishnaswami (2014)** state that citizen journalism in India enables ordinary citizens to report, analyze, and share news through digital platforms, filling gaps left by mainstream media. The **2012 Delhi Gang Rape (Nirbhaya) case** highlighted its impact, as citizens used social media to raise awareness, mobilize protests, and influence legal reforms. Platforms like **IBNLive, Headlines Today**, and various websites support citizen reporting. Overall, citizen journalism empowers individuals, strengthens democracy, and drives social change.

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METHADODOLOGY

1) Types Of Research:

Primary Source- Google Forms

Secondary Source- Articles, Reports

2) Tools Used:

a. Google Forms

b. Online articles

3) Sample Size:

20 Respondents aged 15-30.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The following section presents a detailed analysis and interpretation of the data collected through the survey conducted for this research. The responses have been systematically organized and represented using charts and graphs for clarity. Each question has been analyzed to identify patterns, trends, and insights, which further help in understanding the role of youth-centric news platforms and the influence of citizen journalism on governance.

Section A: Demographic Analysis

AGE GROUP:

Analysis: The majority of respondents (63.2%) are aged 16–18, followed by 26% aged 13-15 and 10.5% aged 25-30.

Interpretation: This indicates that the survey responses are primarily from youth, the main focus of this study, making the findings relevant and reliable.

GENDER:

Analysis: Out of total respondents, 63.2% identified as female, 31.6% as male, and 5.3% preferred not to disclose.

Interpretation: The gender distribution shows a reasonably balanced sample, ensuring diverse perspectives in the study but we still might see a little greater proportion of females that would be influencing the interpretations.

Section B: News Habits

Question 1- Do you follow youth-centric news platforms?

Analysis: Out of the total respondents, 63.2% reported that they follow youth-centric news platforms, while 28% do not.

Interpretation: The majority following such platforms indicates that youth are actively seeking news tailored to their interests. This shows a shift from traditional media to digital, youth-focused news sources.

Question 2- Which youth-centric news platform do you use the most?

Analysis: It shows a very mixed type of responses where, **YOUTH KI AWAAZ** which is India's largest platform for people powered stories is seen to be the most prevalent with over 47.7% people being engaged in it. Followed by other platforms like **THE LOGICAL INDIAN** with

15.8%. While there are many who still do not use any specific platform to consume youth powered news in their daily life.

Interpretation: This suggests that visually engaging , people centered and short-form content is highly influential among youth. News platforms targeting young audiences should prioritize such formats to maximize reach and engagement.

Question 3- How often do you check online news?

Analysis: Out of total respondents, around 52.6% consume online news 2-3 times a week while 26.3% people go through online news daily followed by 10% people who rarely prefer the online news.

Interpretation: Moderate daily engagement reflects that youth are gradually starting to interact with online content which shows that this habit is increasing the exposure to citizen journalism and potentially strengthens their awareness of governance and social issues. And a drastic switch from traditional platform to online platforms.

Question 4- Do you trust news from social media?

Analysis: Out of all the responses, the majority of people trust the social media news sometimes which is around 94.7% and there is a very less number of people who genuinely trust the news.

Interpretation: This shows that people are still very much conscious about whether to trust a social media news or not. There is still a lack of trust and a huge gap between the consumers and the portals which needs to be built in order to strengthen the role of social media news and portals in governance.

Question 5- Do you think citizen journalism influences government decisions?

Analysis: This question was based on a linear scale from 1-5 where 1 meant "Not at all influential" and 5 meant "Highly influential". The highest chosen option was 3 which means individuals are neutral.

Interpretation: It shows that in today's time also individuals are in a big dilemma about whether citizen journalism influences the government decisions or not. It is important for the government to increase accountability and responsiveness in order to gain the trust of its citizens.

Question 6- Have you ever posted about a social issue online?

Analysis: It shows a tie between “YES” and “Sometimes” with 42.1% votes to these options while “NO” is seen less prevalent in this field with only 15.8% votes.

Interpretation: The results suggest that most respondents are open to posting news on social media, but not always consistently. While 42.1% actively share news, an equal percentage do so only in certain situations, indicating that factors like the type of news, its relevance, or credibility influence their decision. The low percentage of “No” (15.8%) shows that very few people completely avoid sharing news, meaning social media is generally accepted as a platform for news sharing, though usage varies depending on context.

Question 7- Which issues are you most likely to post about?

Analysis: It clearly indicates that individuals tend to post more about **Women Safety (42.1%)** and **Civic Issues (31.6%)** while other problems regarding the fields of Environment and Politics remain significant.

Interpretation: It shows that people have started to become more cautious about the issues regarding women safety and civic issues but it also indicates that individuals are not focusing and working much towards education and environmental problems which have become a rising issue in the global politics as well.

Question 8- Rate the credibility of social media news

Analysis: This question was based on a linear scale from 1-5 where 1 meant “ Not at all credible” and 5 meant “Highly credible”. The highest chosen option was 2 and 3 which means individuals still do not consider the social media news as a credible source of information.

Interpretation: Individuals do not consider social media news a credible source and this could be due to various reasons like Rumours, PR stunts and many such issues that come collectively. In order to make it a credible source the youth portals need to first make sure that their news are verified and absolutely correct.

Question 9- How often do you verify news before sharing?

Analysis: Around 63.2% of individuals always verify the news before sharing it while there are still around 30-40% of individuals who circulate the news without cross checking and verifying.

Interpretation: Seeing the high percentage of individuals that are verifying the news before circulating is a very positive sign which prevents unwanted circumstances like rumours and increases the credibility of youth lead news portals while there are still a good percentage of

individuals who still circulate the news without verifying which often leads to devastating consequences. Individuals have to be responsible enough and cautious before sharing the news for the benefit of their own people. They must understand the ways to properly verify the news and then move forward.

KEY FINDINGS OF THIS PROJECT

- **Youth Are Active but Selective News Consumers:** Most respondents (63.2%) follow youth-centric news platforms, showing that young people are keen to stay informed. However, they engage differently like some check news daily, others a few times a week, highlighting varied habits.
- **Trust Is Conditional:** While youth often consume news online, only a small number fully trust it. Most are cautious, reflecting an awareness of misinformation and the need to verify before believing or sharing.
- **Citizen Journalism Sparks Engagement:** A large portion of respondents have posted about social issues online, at least sometimes, especially on topics like women’s safety and civic issues. This shows that youth are willing to contribute their voices but tend to focus on issues that directly resonate with them.
- **Social Media News Is Not Fully Credible Yet:** Ratings for credibility lean toward the middle, showing that while platforms are widely used, young audiences remain skeptical. Verified, accurate reporting is still a key challenge.
- **Influence on Governance Is Limited but Growing:** Respondents remain neutral on whether citizen journalism directly impacts government decisions, suggesting that while awareness and discussion are rising, real policy influence is still uncertain.
- **Platform Preferences Matter:** “Youth Ki Awaaz” emerges as the most popular platform, highlighting that content that is relatable, people-centered, and visually engaging attracts youth attention more than traditional reporting styles.

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CONCLUSION OF THIS PROJECT

This study highlights that today's youth are far from being passive consumers of news, they are active participants in shaping conversations, raising awareness, and bringing attention to social issues through digital platforms. While the findings suggest that citizen journalism does not yet directly influence government policies, it clearly plays a vital role in fostering public dialogue, encouraging civic engagement, and promoting accountability. Youth-centric news portals, such as *Youth Ki Awaaz*, demonstrate that relatable, people-focused, and visually engaging content resonates strongly with young audiences, empowering them to share their voices on topics that matter most, like women's safety and civic concerns.

The cautious approach of youth toward trusting social media news shows a critical awareness, emphasizing the need for verified and responsible reporting. As young people continue to engage selectively, verify information, and post about social issues, they are gradually strengthening the bridge between citizens and governance. With improved credibility, increased participation, and sustained engagement, youth-led news platforms have the potential to evolve from being sources of awareness into genuine tools for social influence, proving that even individual voices can create meaningful ripples of change in society.

GRATITUDE

I would like to sincerely thank the people who took the time to participate in this survey and share their honest thoughts. Your insights made this research meaningful and helped me understand how youth engage with news and citizen journalism in today's digital world.

I am especially grateful to a few close people who supported me throughout this project, offering encouragement, advice, and motivation whenever I needed it. Your guidance made the journey smoother and inspired me to explore the role of youth in shaping conversations and creating awareness.

Finally, I hope this project encourages more young people to responsibly share news, raise awareness, and contribute to positive change. Every voice matters, and together, small actions can make a big difference.

THANK YOU!!

